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The Parable of the Minas (Lk 19:11-28): Trust, Responsibility and Mission

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Abstract: The parable of the minas (Lk 19:11-28), strategically placed at the end of the journey to Jerusalem, is a text considered difficult. On the one hand, it incorporates the parable of the pretender to the throne in the story of the minas/talents; on the other hand, it shows violence of the harsh words of the king. This article proposes a new approach from

pragmalinguistics, analyzing the literary context, linguistic cohesion and communicative coherence. The Lukan communicative strategy proposes trust, responsibility and mission as the keys to reading.

Keywords: Lk 19:11-28, Parable of the Minas, Pragmalinguistics, Trust, Responsibility, Mission

1. INTRODUCTION

Delving into a biblical text is no easy task, but it is always an exciting journey. The Word of God continues to arouse in our day a lively interest, a healthy curiosity and a set of questions, which is why it is still necessary to approach it with pause, to establish a dialogue and to listen to its questions. These attitudes are especially necessary for texts that are considered difficult, as well as for those that are particularly well known.

Difficulties in interpretation and familiarity with the text go hand in hand in the *parable of the minas* (Lk 19:11-28). The narrative importance of this text, strategically placed at the end of the road to Jerusalem, shows a certain vision of the kingdom of God and of the king which require the reader's collaboration in order to be understood. At the same time, the Lukan redactional task leads to the unification in the same account of two apparently autonomous parables: the parable of the minas/talents and the parable of the pretender to the throne.

The parable of the minas has been studied from various points of view: as an authentic parable of Jesus¹; as a response to the delay of the *parousia*²; from a comparative point of view

¹ For J. P. Meier, the parable of the talents/minas is one of the few "very few fortunate parables" that can be traced back to Jesus and are not the fruit of the reflection of the community or the hand of the evangelists, John P. MEIER, *Un juicio marginal. Nueva visión del Jesús histórico: La autenticidad de las parábolas a examen*, V, Estella, Verbo Divino, 2017, 308-341.

² Cf. Luke T. JOHNSON, "The Lukan Kingship Parable (Lk 19:11-27)", *NovT* 24 (1982) 141 (139-159) (<https://doi.org/10.2307/1560555>); Simon GATHERCOLE, "Does the Parable of the Minas Address the Delay of the Parousia? Luke 19:11-27 in its Lukan, Rhetorical and Roman Settings", *ZNW* 115 (2024) 19-50 (<https://doi.org/10.1515/znw-2024-0002>).

with the Matthean account³; from a redactional history⁴; from a historical interest⁵, especially in relation to Archelaus⁶; from a social perspective⁷. In this study, we start from the elements evidenced by the different approaches taken. In this way, it focuses on the analysis of the text as it has been transmitted, noting the unity of the Lukan account⁸.

The challenge posed by Lk 19:11-28 needs to be met by employing new methodological approaches. The communicative

³ A comparative study of the Matthean parallel will not be carried out; rather, in the course of the work, some common or divergent points will be indicated insofar as they shed light on the research. For a parallel analysis of the two parables, cf. Armand PUIG I TÀRRECH, "La parabole des talents (Mt 25:14-30) ou des mines (Lk 19:11-28)", in François REFOULÉ (ed.), *À cause de l'Évangile: Études sur les synoptiques et les Actes*, Fs. J. Dupont (Lectio Divina 123), Paris, Cerf, 1985, 165-193; Pablo Antonio Díez HERRERA, "Las parábolas de los talentos (Mt 25:14-30) y de las minas (Lc 19:11-28): Estudio comparativo y exegético" *Isidorianum* 12 (2003) 273-316 (<https://doi.org/10.46543/isid.0312.1052>); J. Gertrud TÖNSING, "Scolding the «Wicked, Lazy» Servant; Is the Master God?: A Redaction-Critical Study of Matthew 25:14-30 and Luke 19:11-27", *Neotestamentica* 53 (2019) 123-147 (<https://doi.org/10.1353/neo.2019.0013>).

⁴ Cf. Adelbert DENAUX, "The Parable of the Talents/Pounds (Q 19,12-27): A Reconstruction of the Q Text", in Andreas LINDEMANN (ed.), *Sayings Source Q and the Historical Jesus* (BETHL 158), Leuven, Peeters, 2001, 429-460.

⁵ On the historical context of the original telling of the parable, as well as the comparison with some rabbinic parables that shed light on the attitude of the third servant, cf. Robert DORAN, "The Parable of the Talents/Pounds: Apocalyptic Warning or Economic Critique?", *Biblica* 100 (2019) 527-542.

⁶ Cf. Brian SCHULTZ, "Jesus as Archelaus in the Parable of the Pounds (Lk 19:11-27)", *NovT* 49 (2007) 105-127 (<https://doi.org/10.1163/156853607x185339>); Ernest VAN ECK, "Social Memory and Identity: Luke 19:12b-24 and 27", *BTB* 41 (2011) 201-212.

⁷ Cf. J. Duncan. M. DERRETT, "A Horrid Passage in Luke Explained (Lk 19:27)", *ET* 97 (1986) 136-138 (<https://doi.org/10.1177/001452468609700503>); Richard L. ROHRBAUGH, "A Peasant Reading of the Parable of the Talents/Pounds: A Text of Terror?", *BTB* 23 (1993) 32-39 (<https://doi.org/10.1177/014610799302300105>).

⁸ In this line, although with different nuances, we find among others: Ignace DE LA POTTERIE, "La parabole du prétendant à la royauté (Lk 19:11-28)", in François REFOULÉ (ed.), *À cause de l'Évangile: Études sur les synoptiques et les Actes*, Fs. J. Dupont (Lectio Divina 123), Paris, Cerf, 1985, 619-626 (613-641); François BOVON, *El evangelio según San Lucas*, III (BEB 87), Salamanca, Sígueme, 2004, 359-374; Gérard ROSSÉ, *Il Vangelo di Luca: commento esegetico e teologico*, Roma, Città Nuova, 1992, 726-737.

and pragmatic approach⁹ can be useful to offer hermeneutical keys to grasp its deep meaning and its vital importance for Christian readers of any age. In this sense, it is not a one-way and static communication but an interactive one, where sender and receiver can, indeed must, meet each other. The text is understood as a communicative event: the sending and receiving of messages is not simply something that one does “to” another, but a process that one does “with” the other¹⁰.

The study will begin with an analysis of Lk 19:11-28 in its literary context. Subsequently, both the linguistic cohesion and the communicative coherence of the text will be highlighted. Finally, the communicative intention in the pragmatic focus will be highlighted and concluding remarks will be presented. The final aim is to show that the communicative strategy of the parable proposes trust, responsibility and mission as keys to reading.

2. LK 19:11-28 IN ITS LITERARY CONTEXT

This first section deals with the delimitation of the textual unit, as well as the arguments that justify its study in a particular way in a given co-text¹¹. Finally, some textual variants will be analysed.

⁹ “La aproximación pragmalingüística pretende poner de relieve las relaciones tanto a nivel de forma y contenido (cohesión textual) como de significado (coherencia comunicativa), teniendo especialmente presente que el objetivo final es conducir a los interlocutores a interrelacionarse (focalización pragmática)” (Isaac MORENO SANZ, *Jesús y Moisés en diálogo. Significado y función de la figura de Moisés en la obra lucana* (ABE Monografías 79), Estella, Verbo Divino, 2021, 36). On the methodological perspective adopted, cf. Massimo GRILLI – Maurizio GUIDI – Elzbieta M. OBARA (eds.) *Comunicación y pragmática en la exégesis bíblica* (Colección Evangelio y Cultura 6), Estella, Verbo Divino, 2018, 17-105.

¹⁰ Cf. Isaac MORENO SANZ, *Jesús y Moisés en diálogo*, 36-37; Massimo GRILLI, “Interpretazione e azione. L’istanza pragmatica del testo biblico”, in Massimo GRILLI – Maurizio GUIDI – Elzbieta M. OBARA (eds.), *Comunicazione e pragmatica nell’esegesi biblica* (Lectio 10), Cinisello Balsamo, San Paolo - BGP, 2016, 18-21 (11-46).

¹¹ “Por «co-texto» se entiende la porción de discurso, una sección sintáctica, que rodea a una perícopa o pasaje, primordial para entender la organización interna de los textos y los procedimientos de cohesión. Dentro de una obra literaria el co-texto ofrece los elementos textuales necesarios para la comprensión de un determinado pasaje” (Isaac MORENO SANZ, “De

2.1. Delimitation and unity of Lk 19:11-28

At the end of the road to Jerusalem, Luke relates an encounter—Jesus with Zacchaeus in Jericho (Lk 19:1-10)—and a parable—the parable of the minas—. The author, with his characteristic narrative skill, proposes an introduction to the parable (Lk 19:11), which establishes a bridge with the previous encounter, and at the same time it marks a step forward, both by the change of characters and by the change of setting.

In Lk 19:1-10 Zacchaeus is presented as the protagonist of the action, but from v. 10 onwards he disappears. It should be noted that the development of the encounter with Zacchaeus is geographically situated in the city of Jericho (v. 1) while in v. 11 the parable is presented close to Jerusalem. This proximity should be understood as a spatial proximity which opens a new framework for the development of the parable.

As regards the delimitation of the end of the pericope, some authors¹² opt for ending in v. 27 and others¹³, include v. 28. In this sense, vv. 11 and 28 should be considered as the framework, not indifferent, of the parable, which should not be interpreted without it¹⁴. Thus, at the end of the episode (v. 28), it is indicated that Jesus and his companions continue on their way to Jerusalem, leaving a “geographical gap” between their departure from Jericho and their arrival in the vicinity of Jerusalem, which the narrator does not mention, despite the fact that it is a journey of approximately thirty kilometers, not without its dangers¹⁵. The next change of scene in v. 29 presents Jesus marching in the lead (ἔμπροσθεν) near Bethphage and Bethany, thus

los aljibes agrietados a la fuente de aguas vivas. Jr 2,10-13 en clave comunicativa”, *RevBib* 86 [2024], 56).

¹² J. Lambrecht, D. Dormeyer, E. van Eck, B. Schultz, L. Panier, J.A. Fitzmyer, F. Bovon, among others.

¹³ In favour of finalising in v. 28: P.A. Díez Herrera, A. Denaux, J.-N. Aletti, R. Meynet, G. Rossé.

¹⁴ Cf. Jean-Noël ALETTI, *El arte de contar a Jesucristo. Lectura narrativa del evangelio de Lucas* (BEB 77), Salamanca, Sígueme, 1992, 19.

¹⁵ Cf. Joaquín GONZÁLEZ ECHEGARAY, “Geografía y arqueología bíblicas”, in Joaquín GONZÁLEZ ECHEGARAY *et al.* (eds.), *La Biblia en su entorno* (Instrumentos para el Estudio de la Biblia 1) Estella, Verbo Divino, 1990, 54-55.

representing one of the summaries (cf. 9:51; 13:22; 17:11) that support the account of the journey towards Jerusalem.

2.2. Co-text

The close co-text of the parable shows the misunderstanding of those around Jesus, the right use of goods and the kingship of Christ¹⁶. With a careful relationship to the passages immediately preceding and following, Lk 19:11-28 has been considered as the centre of the sequence (Lk 18:31–19:46)¹⁷.

The broad co-text of the pericope would be the account of Jesus' journey to Jerusalem contained in section 9:51–19:44 which occupies the central part of the third Gospel. In this large section, Luke collects the teachings of Jesus, especially through parables, which he combines with some miracles and paradigmatic encounters, where the real narrative logic is that of the journey itself¹⁸. The entry into Jerusalem (v. 45, εἰσελθὼν εἰς τὸ ἱερόν) closes this long pilgrimage, highlighting the cultic aspect of the Holy City: rather than entering Jerusalem, Jesus enters the Temple.

2.3. Textual criticism

No major textual problems are found in Lk 19:11-28. Nevertheless, it is possible to identify two issues that need to be clarified. In v. 11 the proposition ἐγγύς εἶναι Ἱερουσαλήμ

¹⁶ Cf. Jan LAMBRECHT, "La parabola del pretendente al trono (Lc 19,11-27)", in Ettore FRANCO (ed.), *Mysterium Regni, ministerium Verbi*, Bologna, EDB, 2001, 382 (379-390).

¹⁷ The concentric construction, according to Semitic rhetoric, is the figure of composition in which the related units are arranged in such a way that the key to understanding a text is placed in the centre, following the scheme: A B C D | x | D' C' B' A'. In this sense, according to R. Meynet, this stylistic device, as opposed to parallelism, would have a passage (in this case the parable of the minas) at the centre of the sequence, thus emphasising its importance in the co-text. Cf. Roland MEYNET, *Il Vangelo secondo Luca: analisi retorica*, Bologna, EDB, 1994, 665-711.

¹⁸ Cf. Giuseppe SEGALLA, *Teologia biblica del Nuovo Testamento: tra memoria escatologica di Gesù e promessa del futuro regno di Dio* (Logos 8/2), Leumann, Elledici, 2006, 360.

αὐτόν is omitted by various manuscripts (A, K, W, K, Γ, Δ, Θ, *f*¹³, 565, 700, 892, 1424), although it is found in most ancient manuscripts (κ, B, L, 1241, among others). With regard to external criticism, the version maintained by NA²⁸, which includes the reference to Jerusalem, seems to be well attested. Similarly, the reference to the Holy City in 19:28 is presented as a criterion of internal criticism, by way of inclusion, and is consistent with the importance that Luke gives to the Holy City in the development of the journey towards it.

V. 25 is omitted by some codices (D, W, 69, 565) and some ancient translations (Itala^{b,d,e}, Syriac, Coptic^{bo}, among others), but it appears in most of the eldest Greek codices. For stylistic reasons it seems to be unrelated to vv. 24 and 26, so that if it were removed there would be a more fluid relationship between both. However, it should be retained, since it is not only the *lectio difficilior*, but it also agrees with the narrative¹⁹. Internal criticism also supports the intervention of v. 25 as a Lukan stylistic device, which picks up the protest of some characters in the parables (cf. Lk 15:25-32; 20:9-18).

3. LINGUISTIC COHESION OF LK 19:11-28

Cohesion has to do with the linguistic (lexical and grammatical) connection between the parts of the parable. In other words, the aim of this section is not to explain the meaning of the text, but its construction. The text, as its own etymology evokes, can be compared to a weaving, constituted by a web or a warp of words²⁰. Some authors propose concentric structures²¹, while others point to two parallel parts²². Our proposal

¹⁹ Cf. Bruce M. METZGER, *A Textual Commentary on the Greek New Testament*, Stuttgart, Deutsche Bibelgesellschaft, ²1994, 144

²⁰ Cf. MORENO SANZ, *Jesús y Moisés en diálogo*, 36-37.

²¹ Cf. MEYNET, *Il Vangelo secondo Luca*, 684-685; Detlev DORMEYER, "La parábola de las minas en el campo de las biografías didácticas de Pedro el pobre y Pablo el rico en los Hechos de los Apóstoles", in Massimo GRILLI – Daniel GÁNDARA – Cordula LANGNER (eds.), *Riqueza y solidaridad en la obra de Lucas* (Colección Evangelio y Cultura. Monografías 3), Estella, Verbo Divino, 2006, 250 (243-258).

²² Cf. DE LA POTTERIE, "La parabole du prétendant à la royauté", 613-641; Adelbert DENAUX, "The Parable of the King-Judge (Lk 19:12-28) and Its

divides the parable into three acts framed by the introduction and the conclusion²³.

3.1. Narrative introduction and conclusion (vv. 11,28)

Luke offers a series of identifying signs that demand the reader's attention before the parables (Lk 14:7). These words introduce a story into the plot, warning the reader that he or she will have to decipher it²⁴. The versicle 28 links with v. 11 by way of inclusion: it looks back to the events just narrated in order to continue the narrative²⁵.

Who are the recipients of the information in these verses? The versicle 11 does not make clear exactly the geographical place where Jesus pronounces the parable. Although the previous characters have disappeared from the scene, the author refers to a group that has heard what has happened. Exactly who this group is is not defined, except by the 3rd person plural pronoun (αὐτῶν, v. 11). It is likely that this pronoun refers to the anonymous background about which Jesus' activity takes place, underlining the tension and faith of those who seek him. Some authors narrow the circle and relate αὐτῶν to the disciples of Jesus in the strict sense²⁶. Thus, it would seem consistent to situate the scene in the house of Zacchaeus²⁷, so that they would be few and not a large number, since for

Relation to the Entry Story (Lk 19:29-44)", ZNW 93 (2002) 35-57 (<https://doi.org/10.1515/zntw.2002.007>).

²³ The difficulties of vv. 12, 14, 24a, 27 in the narrative do not detract from Luke's redactional task in the parable, which is precisely why a synchronic study of the parable is proposed. Nevertheless, it is necessary to value diachronic studies which take into account the previous stages of the material which Luke masterfully relates.

²⁴ Cf. Daniel MARGUERAT, *Parábola* (Cuaderno Bíblico 75) Estella, Verbo Divino, ³1992, 12.

²⁵ The use of the participles ἀκουόντων (v. 11) and εἰπῶν (v. 28) accentuate the framing function of both verses, bringing the hearing (ἀκούω) and the word (λέγω) into relationship.

²⁶ Cf. Jan LAMBRECHT, "Reading and Rereading Lk 18,31-22,6", in François REFOULÉ (ed.), *À cause de l'Évangile: Etudes sur les synoptiques et les Actes*, Fs. J. Dupont (Lectio Divina 123), Paris, Cerf, 1985, 597 (585-612).

²⁷ Cf. LAMBRECHT, "The Parable of the Pretender to the Throne (Lk 19:11-27)", 382.

obvious reasons they would not fit in his house. One way or another, the author does not specify the location where the parable is pronounced or who exactly hear it. The only thing that stands out is the proximity to Jerusalem, and that is what is important for linguistic cohesion.

3.2. Act I (vv. 12-14)

The very beginning of the parable is the expression: εἶπεν οὖν (v. 12a). The first act it is very brief and many points are left unsaid, leaving the reader with numerous questions²⁸. This act is divided into three steps according to the characters: the man of noble birth (v. 12); the ten servants (v. 13); the countrymen (v. 14).

This beginning is devoid of precise information²⁹, suffice it to note the use of the anonymous ἄνθρωπος τις. In order to become king he sets out on a journey to a distant region, again undefined. On the level of narrative coherence, v. 14 is strange. Why don't the countrymen want him to reign over them? And above all, why do they say this after an objectively praiseworthy action such as the king's trust in his servants? The development of the narrative will attempt to answer these and other questions that have been raised in this first act.

In v. 14 we find the shift from the aorist, which has hitherto been predominant, to the imperfect. The hatred of the countrymen is presented with the verb μισέω in the imperfect (ἐμίσουν) and is placed in the continuing background of the action³⁰. Moreover, the actions against the future king are presented in duplicate. On the one hand, there are the

²⁸ Cf. ALETTI, *El arte de contar a Jesucristo*, 121.

²⁹ The fact that names are not given is striking and is understandable because of the literary genre to which the text belongs. Each of the characters is presented by the function they represent in the story, and it will be the narrative itself that adds the necessary information to understand them as a whole. In any case, both anonymity and proper names, even in parables (cf. Lk 16:19-31), can function communicatively as a strategy that favours the reader's identification with the characters.

³⁰ Cf. Alviero NICCACCI, "Dall'aoristo all'imperfetto o dal primo piano allo sfondo. Un paragone tra sintassi greca e sintassi ebraica", *Studia Biblica Franciscani. Liber Annuus* 42 (1992) 87-88 (85-108).

countrymen who do not want him and, on the other, the embassy sent by them. The number of the countrymen and the embassy remains unknown, overshadowed by what is considered important at the narrative level: “we do not want him to reign over us”.

3.3. Act II (vv. 15-23)

The second act begins with the typically Lukan construction *καὶ ἐγένετο*³¹ which serves as an introduction. Immediately afterwards, the narrator indicates the king’s intention (v. 15). Narratively, seven of the ten initial servants disappear from the scene, of whom it is not indicated whether they are condemned or rewarded. The narrator’s skill is also shown in the omission, i.e. by not speaking of the servants’ conduct either during the absence of the lord-king or even during the dialogue. Similarly, despite the objective importance of the fact of becoming king or the way in which the delivered mine produces benefits, these aspects are omitted, since he is interested in other elements³².

Again in this act the protagonist is the man of noble birth who has become king. He is the character who remains in the scene throughout the whole act while the three servants pass by one after the other. With these three servants the narrator presents three evaluative points of view³³. The first servant receives a positive evaluation by the king: *εὖγε, ἀγαθὲ δοῦλε*, fostering a “sympathetic” identification due to the positive relationship between the reader and a character

³¹ Cf. Jo Ann M. GAULT, “The Discourse Function of ‘kai egeneto’ in Luke and Acts. Statement of Responsibility”, *Occasional Papers in Translation and Textlinguistics* 4 (1990) 391 (388- 399) (<https://doi.org/10.2986/tren.004-0041>). In v. 16 the narrator begins the series of dialogues with the servants with the construction *παρεγένετο δὲ* which resembles in terms of narrative function shown by *καὶ ἐγένετο*.

³² Cf. Louis PANIER, “Récit et figure dans la paraboles des mines (Luc 19): Un modèle pour une sémiotique du discours”, *Sémiotique et Bible* 117 (2005) 36 (20-45)

³³ Cf. Daniel MARGUERAT – Yvan BOURQUIN, *Cómo leer los relatos bíblicos: iniciación al análisis narrativo* (Presencia Teológica 106), Santander, Sal Terrae, 2000, 113-117.

in the story. The dialogue with the second servant is presented in a similar, though not exactly the same way. The fact that the quantity changes is of no great narrative significance. The second has done well while the first has done excellently. Therefore, what changes narratively is not the presentation of the servant, but the king's response. Even so, the king appreciates the attitude of the second servant during his absence and maintains his trust by granting him power over five cities³⁴.

Despite the differences noted between the first and second servant, both are presented in contrast to the king's "dialogue" with the third servant (vv. 20-23)³⁵. In v. 20 the third servant appears and his entry on the scene is on the same level as the previous servants since they have also pronounced the vocative κύριε. The appeal is the same, while the interjection (ιδού) opens the way to several differences. Firstly, the attitude of the servant who begins by returning the mina. Secondly, he is the only one who formulates a judgement on himself and on the king, a fundamentally negative verdict, which corresponds to elements that do not emerge from the story. Thus, narratively, the same question arises as with the actions of the countrymen who did not want him as king: the narrative does not provide the necessary grounds for such a judgement. Lastly, the king's reaction to him is a repetition of the verbs of judgement that the servant had first uttered.

As in the first act, a significant shift from the aorist to the imperfect can be identified (εἶχον, v. 20; ἐφοβούμην, v. 21). Both what he "had" and what he "feared" belong to the past on a continuous basis. The narrative returns to the foreground in v.

³⁴ The brevity of this second encounter is due to the desire for narrative economy and, in order to avoid monotony, the text simplifies this second dialogue. The second servant uses a banal verb: ἐποίησεν, ("made"), where the first, in a more stilted way, said προσηγάσαστο ("has produced"). In this sense it should be added that the author is slowly inducing a certain evaluation of the third servant's performance. That is, he places the performance of the second servant halfway between the first and the third.

³⁵ To the parallelism between the first and second servant is now added a parallel structure with certain similarities (C, B, A C', B', A'), cf. PUGI TARRÉCH, "La parabole des talents", 177-178.

21 (εἶ, αἴρεις, θερίζεις) which alternates with the aorist, to describe the king. The versicles 21-22 are very intense —syntactically speaking— due to the use by the servant and the king of five verbs, one immediately after the other.

3.4. Act III (vv. 24-27)

In the third act “those present” (καὶ τοῖς παρῆστων) enter the scene (καὶ τοῖς παρῆστων) who until now had gone unnoticed³⁶. From the point of view of the internal coherence of the narrative, they have been mute witnesses of the events barely narrated. To them he addresses in the first passage (vv. 24-26)³⁷ while in the second (v. 27) he refers to the countrymen in v. 14 referred to as “these enemies of mine”. The adverb πλὴν, used as a conjunction at the beginning of the sentence in v. 27, has the function of introducing the final sentence of the parable.

By taking the mine from the third servant and giving it to the first, both characters are in some way present in the action even though they do not intervene. Thus, in the third act, the different characters and the different elements that have been appearing throughout the parable enter the scene once again. In this way, the narrator aims to reveal the meaning of the parable to everyone and to give the reader the necessary clues to understand how the parable unfolds. Finally, with this third act, a certain narrative model is shown, a singular form of scheme and discursive model where the characters and the elements are interwoven to constitute a narrative plot that envelops the reader and keeps him in tension until the end of the story.

³⁶ The king addresses them with two imperatives (ἄρατε, δότε), so that with this device the tension created in the previous verse by the rhetorical question is kept alive by increasing, if possible, the dialectical rigidity.

³⁷ The two future tense verbs in v. 26 (δοθήσεται and ἀρθήσεται) are presented as the result of the judgment (κρινῶ). With the use of this tense, the author refers to a past event, so that the previous action gives rise to a future judgement. The reader is led to keep in mind a judgement that goes beyond the boundaries of the text itself.

4. COMMUNICATIVE COHERENCE

The aim of this section is to understand the text as a whole. The aim is not to analyse the individual terms that comprise the story but rather to focus on their meaning in this particular textual unit.

4.1. Narrative introduction (v. 11)

The narrative introduction does not appear in the Matthean parallel which begins abruptly³⁸. This has led some to undervalue this introductory verse in order to find the closest account to the exact words of Jesus³⁹.

The journey to Jerusalem (9:51-19:44) forms the backbone of Luke's Gospel and runs through the narrative. Thus, v. 11 reminds the reader of the road travelled, but above all it indicates to him the nearness of the Holy City. The pilgrimage⁴⁰ to the Temple was obligatory for every adult Jew. However, in the context of the Lukan community the question might arise: what happens after the events of 70 AD? For Christians, the problem of the Temple was not solved by its destruction alone, nor was it solved for Judaism, which hoped that the Temple would be rebuilt. Luke solved the problem through his Christology: Jesus is the presence of God, because in Christ glory (כְּבוֹד/δόξα) and spirit are related⁴¹. In this way the two motives indicated by the narrator are intertwined: the nearness to Jerusalem and the belief that the manifestation of the Kingdom of God was imminent.

Jesus has announced the Kingdom but not the moment of its manifestation⁴² which, on the other hand, is not revealed

³⁸ Cf. DÍEZ HERRERA, "Las parábolas de los talentos", 287.

³⁹ Cf. SCHULTZ, "Jesus as Archelaus", 110-111.

⁴⁰ On the pilgrimage to Jerusalem, cf. Joachim JEREMIAS, *Jerusalén en tiempos de Jesús: estudio económico y social del mundo del Nuevo Testamento*, Madrid, Cristiandad, 1980, 171.

⁴¹ Cf. Armand BARUS – Dany Christopher, "Jesus, the personified temple in Lukan 'L'". *HTS* 80 (2024), a9527. (<https://doi.org/10.4102/hts.v80i1.9527>).

⁴² Cf. François BOVON, *Luke the Theologian: Fifty-five Years of Research (1950-2005)*, Waco, TX, Baylor University Press, 2006, 15-16.

in the parable either. Throughout the whole journey Jesus was accompanied and questions were raised, some of which he himself answered explicitly, others will be answered in the course of his ministry. The Pharisees ask him: “When is the kingdom of God coming?” (17,20a), expressing the question along the lines of other questions about the Kingdom (Lk 17,20-21; 19,11; 21,31; Acts 1,6) which do not refer to its nature but rather to the moment of its coming⁴³.

The Lukan narrative, through progressive revelation and gradual deepening, intertwines the Kingdom and the King, showing little by little what only in the work as a whole the reader will be able to understand. Thus, the Kingdom of God and the person of Jesus are always linked, so that one cannot speak of the Kingdom of God without Χριστός, nor of Jesus without βασιλεία⁴⁴.

4.2. Act I (vv. 12-14)

a) The noble man (v. 12)

The introductory syntagma ἄνθρωπος τις has appeared before (Lk 10:30; 14:2.16; 15:11; 16:1.19). It is used often with a predicate which determines it⁴⁵. In this case, the predicative adjective εὐγενής fulfils the function of determining this man. According to the context he is a distinguished man, a pretender to the throne. The verb πορεύομαι means “to go, to set out, to walk”⁴⁶. This man goes εἰς χώραν μακρὰν (“to a distant region”). It echoes here the march of the youngest son

⁴³ Cf. Vittorio FUSCO, “«Punto di vista» e «lettore implicito» in due testi escatologici (Lc 19,11-28; Atti 1,6-8)”, in Vittorio FUSCO (ed.), *Da Paolo a Luca. Studi su Luca-Atti vol I* (Studi biblici 124) Brescia, Paideia, 2000, 204 (203-228).

⁴⁴ Cf. Agustín del AGUA PÉREZ, “The Lukan Narrative of the «Evangelization of the Kingdom of God», in Joseph VERHEYDEN (ed.), *The Unity of Luke-Acts: Colloquium Biblicum Lovaniense* (BETHL 142), Leuven, Peeters, 1999, 652 (639-661).

⁴⁵ Cf. Joseph A. FITZMYER, *El Evangelio según san Lucas, IV*, Madrid, Cristianidad, 2005, 78.

⁴⁶ Along the road to Jerusalem this verb appears frequently, cf. 9:51,52,53,56,57; 10:38; 13:33; 17:11

in the parable known as the parable of the prodigal son (εἰς χῶρον μακρῶν, 15,13). In both cases the less important thing is the place, but rather what happens there: squandering one's fortune or becoming a king.

Λαβεῖν ἑαυτῷ βασιλείαν is the purpose of the journey which has been related by many authors to the historical episode of Archelaus (4), son of Herod the Great⁴⁷. This information may come from a historical event that took place in Palestine, however, its incorporation into the parable is due to reasons of narrative credibility⁴⁸.

The context of Jesus' kingship, which unifies the final part of the journey to Jerusalem and his arrival in the Holy City (18:31-19:46), is different from the context of judgment in the Matthean parallel⁴⁹. The difference between judge and king in today's society is quite clear and delimited, but this was not the case in the Ancient Near East. The context of Matthew is basically not so different from that of Luke. Matthew links the parable of the talents to the judgment and Luke, due to different interests, emphasises the concepts of king and kingship⁵⁰.

The v. 12 concludes with the verb ὑποστρέφω ("to return", 35x in the NT; 32x in Lk-Acts), which together with the coordinating copulative conjunction καί places on the same syntactic level both actions: to become king and to return. Thus, the idea of return is in the primary intention of the story and marks two periods of presence with an interval of absence. This fact has led to a reading in an eschatological key: Jesus leaving to return as King⁵¹. This interpretation moves away from the narrative horizon of the story and intends to read the whole episode in an

⁴⁷ Cf. SCHULTZ, "Jesus as Archelaus", 111.

⁴⁸ This moderate stance can help to unfold the full potential of the parable, cf. ROHRBAUGH, "A Peasant Reading", 33.

⁴⁹ The parable of the talents (Mt 25:14-30) is in an eschatological and judgmental co-text, preceded by the parable of the ten maidens (25:1-13) and followed by the final judgment (25:31-46). Both are part of the great eschatological discourse of Jesus in chapters 24-25.

⁵⁰ This is the basic approach of DENAUX's article, "The Parable of the King-Judge (Lk 19:12-28)", 35-57.

⁵¹ Note the connection between the return (ὑποστρέφω) of the king and the beginning of the final judgment Mt 25:31a: "for when I return" (ὅταν δέη).

eschatological key when in reality, as it will be seen later, it is a Christological and ecclesiological perspective⁵².

b) Trust (v. 13)

The pretender to the throne calls “ten servants” (δέκα δούλους) who could act on behalf of their master “in financial and mercantile transactions, according to the system then current in Jewish law”⁵³. The fact that the number of servants is ten, in contrast to the three in the Matthean parallel, may be due, according to F. Bovon, to a Jewish rule, according to which a minimum number of men is necessary for a synagogue community to have a legitimate existence⁵⁴. This interpretation is probable, but perhaps the most important thing to note is the symbolic component of the number ten. On the other hand, in the development of the story the number ten disappears for the sake of another number, also symbolic⁵⁵.

The mina is a Greek unit of measurement and currency, which corresponded to about 570g by weight (Dt 22:19; Ez 45:12). It is mentioned as a coin in 1Macc 14:24. The following table may help to understand the equivalences⁵⁶:

1 denarius	Salary for a day's work
1 mina	100 denarii
1 mina	0.016 talents
1 mina	0.34 kilograms
1 talent	60 minas
1 talent	20.4 kilograms

⁵² This is the position broadly maintained by DE LA POTTERIE, “La parabole du prétendant à la royauté (Lk 19:11-28)”, 619-626.

⁵³ J. Duncan M. DERRETT, “Law in the New Testament: The Parable of the Talents and two Logia”, ZNW 56 (1966) 187-188 (184-195) (<https://doi.org/10.1515/zntw.1965.56.3-4.184>).

⁵⁴ BOVON, *El Evangelio según san Lucas*, III, 363.

⁵⁵ For a study of the symbolic component of numbers in the NT, cf. Mikeal C. PARSONS, “Exegesis «by the Numbers»: Numerology and the New Testament”, *Perspectives in Religious Studies* 35 (2008) 25-43.

⁵⁶ Cf. JEREMIAS, *Jerusalén en tiempos de Jesús*, 139-142.

The sum received, one mina each, is small compared to the talents of Mt, especially since in Luke we are dealing with a king⁵⁷. What is really important, however, is that the mina have been given, given as a gift. Thus, to insist on the amount of the gift is to lose sight of the essential aspect of the gratitude of the gift entrusted to the ten employees⁵⁸.

With the donation of the mine, the servants receive a command: *πραγματεύσασθε ἐν ᾧ ἔρχομαι* (“negotiate while I return”). The verb *πραγματεύομαι*, which is not uncommon in Greek, appears in the NT only on this occasion and means to take up work, to tie oneself with, to concern oneself with, to exploit, to traffic, to transact business, to pursue a professional career⁵⁹. The nuance is more that of “exploit” than of “increase the value of something”, and presupposes an activity rather than a skill⁶⁰.

One of the difficult points of this first act is the understanding of this action. The Torah warns against the accumulation of wealth, especially unjust wealth, in the same sense that the prophets will develop against social injustice⁶¹. Thus, bargaining or exploitation as a way of making unlimited wealth is intrinsically perverse⁶². Added to this is the Lukan radicalism against wealth as an obstacle to the acceptance of the Kingdom of God and human fraternity⁶³.

⁵⁷ Cf. ROSSÉ, *Il Vangelo di Luca*, 731.

⁵⁸ Cf. FITZMYER, *El Evangelio según san Lucas*, IV, 80.

⁵⁹ Cf. BOVON, *El Evangelio según san Lucas*, III, 364.

⁶⁰ Cf. Id. 364.

⁶¹ Cf. P. Rota SCALABRINI, “Il primo Testamento e la ricchezza: benedizione o tentazione?”, *PSV* 42 (2000) 17 (11-29).

⁶² ROHRBAUGH, “A Peasant Reading”, 34, preserved by Eusebius (Theophania

⁶³ Cf. Gérard ROSSÉ, “Il denaro e la ricchezza nell’evangelista Luca”, *PSV* 42 (2000) 128 (119-130). On the wealth-poverty binomial in Luke’s Gospel, cf. Pedro CABELLO MORALES, “*Tened cuidado y guardaos de toda codicia*”: *Hacia una interpretación conciliadora del tema riqueza-pobreza en Lc-Hch a partir del análisis socio-retórico de Lc 12,13-34* (ABE Monographs 52), Estella, Verbo Divino, 2011, 23-45.

c) The countrymen (v. 14)

The versicle 14 contains an aside in the parable of the minas to narrate the dissent of the πολῖται (“countrymen”). The hatred of the countrymen (ἐμίσουν αὐτόν) is not improvised, but originates outside the story and manifests itself within it. Likewise, as a result of this hostility, the text indicates what they do—they send an embassy after him⁶⁴— and what they say as a group—“we do not want him to reign over us”—.

4.3. Act II (19:15-23)

a) The return (v. 15)

D. L. Bock interprets this verse in the light of Jesus’ relationship to the Father⁶⁵. What is undoubtedly evident is the subordination that affects even the king himself. While the man of noble family “gives” (δίδωμι) to his servants ten minas, he himself is also presented as subordinated since the kingdom has been received (λαμβάνω). Thus, both the servants and the king himself have someone above them. Similarly, the focus is not on the amount of money received, but rather on the king’s generosity: he does not want to oppress, demand, collect, but to elevate those who are worthy of trust⁶⁶.

b) Servants (vv. 16-23)

b.1. The first servant (vv. 16-17)

The construction παρεγένετο δέ marks the entry on the scene of the first servant (ὁ πρῶτος). As noted above, the presence of the verb δίδωμι (vv. 13.15) indicates that the mine had been a gift, just as the remuneration is: it is the minas that bear fruit (προσεργάζομαι) for their own sake. Contrary to Mt, Luke does not stress the work done by the servants⁶⁷.

⁶⁴ Again the Archelaus episode resonates, cf. SCHULTZ, “Jesus as Archelaus”, 117.

⁶⁵ Cf. Darrell L. BOCK, *Luke*, II (Baker Exegetical Commentary on the New Testament 3B), Grand Rapids, MI, Baker, 1996, 1535.

⁶⁶ Cf. ALETTI, *El arte de contar a Jesucristo*, 124.

⁶⁷ Cf. PUIG I TÀRRECH, “La parabole des talents”, 184-185.

The percentage gained by the servants in Luke is much higher—even exaggerated⁶⁸—than in Matthew. Again, the king’s trust in his servant stands out, who believes his word when he indicates what was produced by the mina as much as he trusted in entrusting it to him: if he trusts the servant to deliver the mina to him, how cannot he give credit to his word? In this sense, the king begins by assessing the action of the first servant: εὗγε, ἀγαθὲ δούλε responding to the vocative κύριε uttered by the same servant.

The new mission, which goes from small to great (Lk 16:10), is related to the new status: while the man of noble birth gives part of his goods, now that he has become king he shares his authority. More than a reward—an incentive to carry out a task—it is a new mission⁶⁹.

b.2. The second servant (vv. 18-19)

The encounters of the first and the second servant are presented in a parallel, but not similar way: the reader must pay attention to the small details. Apparently, two modes of action are shown: that of the first two servants and that of the third⁷⁰. It will be seen below whether there are pragmatic elements that make us think that there are three actions.

We note three differences between v. 16 and v. 18. The first is the order of the words when referring to the king. While the first servant, before presenting his work, acknowledges the dignity of his master by calling him κύριε, in the case of the second servant the order is reversed: first he mentions the mine and in the second place we find the vocative referring to his master⁷¹. The second difference seems to be due to a greater

⁶⁸ Legal interest rates in the Roman Empire during the first century AD could be as high as 12%, rarely as high as 34%. Therefore, the 1000% earnings of the first serf are more hyperbole than historical data and are calculated to provoke public astonishment. Cf. ROHRBAUGH, “A Peasant Reading”, 35.

⁶⁹ Cf. PUIG I TÀRRECH, “La parabole des talents”, 185.

⁷⁰ “El valor de la repetición literaria consiste en agudizar el contraste entre los dos empleados cumplidores y el improductivo” (FITZMYER, *El Evangelio según san Lucas*, IV, 82).

⁷¹ Cf. John NOLLAND, *Luke*, III (Word Biblical Commentary 35c), Dallas, TX, Word Books, 1993, 915.

fluency of the narrative, so that the verb *προσεργάζομαι* is replaced by a more common one (*ποιέω*). The third difference is in the quantity produced: ten minas in the case of the first servant and five in the case of the second. This change does not pose any great problems at the narrative level either, although it does mark a certain contrast between the two performances, since the second servant has been less concerned.

Also the king's response to the second servant (v. 19) is presented in parallel to the response to the first servant (v. 17). Three differences can be identified between the two interventions. The first, the most important, is elimination of both the initial commendation (*εὖγε, ἀγαθὲ δούλε*) and the allusion to the proverb of 16:10 (*ὅτι ἐν ἐλαχίστῳ πιστὸς ἐγένου*). The expression *καὶ σύ* —*καί* with adverbial value— in v. 19 connects the answer given to the first servant with that of the second. Yet the force of the words dedicated to the first servant is only remotely captured by the expression “you too”. The second difference is due to a search for narrative economy which replaces the most elaborated construction *ἴσθι ἐξουσίαν ἔχων ἐπάνω* of v. 17 by a simpler one: *ἐπάνω γίνου*. The third difference shows the coherence of the narrative, if the ten minas of the first servant correspond the power over ten cities, the five minas of the second will belong the power over five cities. In short, the dialogue with the first two servants allows us to get to know the king better⁷².

b.3. The third servant (vv. 20-23)

At first glance, the presentation of the third servant resembles that of the previous two. At the narrative level it is strange that he is not called the third but *ὁ ἕτερος* (“the other”), marking the difference with those who came first⁷³. In any case,

⁷² Cf. Carlo BROCCARDO, *Vangelo di Luca* (Nuovo Testamento. Commento esegetico e spirituale), Roma, Castelvechi, 2012, 194.

⁷³ With regard to the first two servants, “the first” and “the second” were indicated, so that the consistency with regard to the initial number of ten servants was not completely broken. However, calling the third servant “the other” leaves out the initial number, marks the differences and makes the reader, from the outset, to situate himself differently.

this small detail does not prevent the reader from expecting a similar performance to the “others”, at least when the third servant addresses the king by calling him κύριε. The interjection ἰδοῦ opens the way to differences. The function of this is twofold: to address the king and at the same time to catch the reader’s attention.

V. 20b presents the actions of the third servant. The mina is returned to the king indicating what he had done with it during his absence. He “had” (εἶχον) the mina in a handkerchief⁷⁴, seeking its safety and his own. The third servant indicates in v. 21 the motive which has led him to act in this way: fear. In this case, it is a fear of a specific person who is identified by the personal pronoun in the accusative. It is necessary to avoid the theological weight of the motive of fear before the epiphany or the “God-fearers”⁷⁵. The verb φοβέομαι usually appears in Luke within the teachings of Jesus as an exhortation to “not fear”, addressed mostly to the disciples, but also to his adversaries⁷⁶. The author uses this verb in the imperfect: ἐφοβούμην γὰρ σε (“for I feared you”). A parenthesis is thus established in the narrative to communicate, by means of the imperfect, an important detail of the main information. Fear becomes the cause of the third servant’s actions: the fear of the strict figure of his master paralyzes his initiative; that is why he did not manage the money put at his disposal, but only kept it⁷⁷.

⁷⁴ The term σουδάριον is a Latinism equivalent to *sudarium* and translates as “handkerchief”. As for the custom of hiding money to protect it, it is documented in Jewish sources, but it was not considered as safe as burying it in the ground, cf. Bruce J. MALINA - Richard L. ROHRBAUGH, *Los evangelios sinópticos y la cultura mediterránea del siglo I: comentario desde las ciencias sociales*, Estella, Verbo Divino, 1996, 372-373.

⁷⁵ This expression appears as many as five times in Acts, cf. Thomas M. FINN, “The God-Fearers Reconsidered”, *CBQ* 47 (1985) 80 (75-84); Max WILCOX, “The «God-Fearers» in Acts A Reconsideration”, *JSNT* 13 (1981) 102-122 (<https://doi.org/10.1177/0142064x8100401307>) 102-122.

⁷⁶ Cf. Maurizio COMPIANI, *Fuga, silenzio e paura: la conclusione del Vangelo di Mc: studio di Mc 16,1-20* (Tesi Gregoriana. Serie Teologia 182), Roma, GBP, 2011, 64.

⁷⁷ Cf. Rainer DILLMANN – César MORA PAZ, *Comentario al Evangelio de Lucas: un comentario para la actividad pastoral* (Evangelio y Cultura. Comentarios 2), Estella, Verbo Divino, 2006, 430.

At this point in the narrative, the question any reader might ask: Why was the third servant afraid? The answer is given by the servant himself: “because you are a severe man”. The image that the third servant reflects does not match the narrative of the two previous servants. The adjective *αυστηρός* reflects a prior opinion to the narrative that conditions his action, as well as the two complementary images: the first belongs to the language of banking; the second image belongs to the world of agriculture.

The third servant, in short, doesn't speak of himself but of the king. He does so with harsh words, to the extent that, instead of acknowledging the mine's lack of performance, i.e. its lack of interest and productivity, he accuses the king of being a lazy man himself. The two images used are on the same line: taking as one's own something that is not one's own in order to acquire one's own profit from the work of others.

From the words of the third servant it is clear that he did not know his master properly, or that he was carried away by his prejudices. Precisely because of this, the third servant will be judged in vv. 22-23 by his own words, which have projected a certain image of the king: the judgement takes place *ἐκ τοῦ στόματός σου* (“from your mouth”). The author uses this metonymy⁷⁸ in an emphatic position. These words constitute the key element for the judgment. The king does not condemn the servant for his feeling (fear), nor for his behaviour during his absence (lack of activity), but for the words he utters against him.

The third servant has pronounced his own condemnation which is only ratified by the king, altering the order and qualification of the first two: *πονηρὸν δούλε* (“bad servant”). In v. 22b the king repeats the same words of the third servant which resonate in the reader as a reiterative echo that acquires a new meaning on a pragmatic level in the king's mouth⁷⁹. By repeating the servant's words, the king seems to

⁷⁸ The king, wishing to refer to the words of the third servant, uses the mouth—which would be the instrument—for the sound it produces. Among the different types of metonymy, the author takes the effect (the words) for the cause (the mouth).

⁷⁹ Cf. Ernest VAN ECK, “Do Not Question my Honour: A Social-Scientific Reading of the Parable of the Minas (Lk 19:12b-24, 27)”, *HTS Theological*

accept this assessment of himself; in any case, he does nothing to refute it⁸⁰.

The versicle 24 raises a number of questions that are part of the pragmatic strategy: if the king did not want either the mina or the interests, two questions arise: What does he want? Why does he indicate an action where the mina and the interests come to the forefront? As it will be seen, while the mine may be important, the focus is on trust and responsibility for the mission entrusted to him.

4.4. Act III (19:24-27)

a) The dialogue (vv. 24-26)

The king (v. 24) addresses those present who are not identified. Throughout the narrative, the author has offered the model reader different possibilities of identification: the Lord, the diligent servants and the lazy servant⁸¹ to which we must now add the anonymous chorus (courtiers, the king's guard, the remaining servants?) of those who were present (παρεστῶσιν v. 24). In any case, those "present" are people of the king's confidence, who have witnessed what happened to the three servants.

The versicle 25 records the protest of those present. From the narrative point of view it seems incongruous with the story, since it does not take into account that the first servant already has power over ten cities⁸². In any case, what is revealed is the protest against a situation that is considered to be unjust.

The versicles 26-27 raise various problems of interpretation. The traditional reading, influenced by the Matthean parallel, would be as follows: whoever has a talent (using the word in the modern sense) of any kind and does not use it,

Studies 67 (2011) (<https://doi.org/10.4102/hts.v67i3.977>), 7-8.

⁸⁰ Cf. Joel B. GREEN, *The Gospel of Luke* (The New International Commentary on the New Testament), Cambridge, MA, Eerdmans, 1997, 681.

⁸¹ Cf. DORMEYER, "La parábola de las minas", 252.

⁸² Cf. I. Howard MARSHALL, *The Gospel of Luke: A Commentary on the Greek Text* (The New International Commentary on the New Testament), Cambridge, MA, Paternoster, 1978, 708.

he loses it because of that. On the contrary, he who has a talent and uses it to the full, finds that it develops and grows⁸³. According to most authors⁸⁴, v. 26 takes up a logos of Jesus which originally belonged to another context. The use of the two verbs in the future tense (δοθήσεται, ἀρθήσεται) gives it a lasting value in time, reinforced by the passive forms with periphrastic value⁸⁵.

b) The punishment (v. 27)

The harsh words to the “enemies” in v. 27 (cf. v. 14) reflect a tone of violence that strikes the reader. This harshness recalls the violence of the despots of antiquity⁸⁶. Some authors make an allegorical reading: the parable is intended to put an end to the forces of evil⁸⁷. Rather, the description of the punishment should be understood from the historical-salvific vision of the Lukan parable.

The condemnation for the king’s enemies is the worst of condemnations: the death penalty. The verb κατασφάζω is a *hapax legomenon* and means “to kill, to sacrifice”⁸⁸. The punishment is described in crude terms but in accordance with the usages of the time. Moreover, for the author of the third

⁸³ Cf. LEON MORRIS, *The Gospel According to Matthew*, Grand Rapids, MI, Eerdmans, 1992, 632.

⁸⁴ Cf. TIMOTHY A. FRIEDRICHSEN, “«To One Who Has...»: Mk 4,25 (Mt 25,29; Lk 19,26): A Note on the Independence of Mk 4,25 from Q 19,26 and o, the Sayings Cluster of Mk 4,21-25”, *Ephemerides Theologicae Lovanienses* 82 (2006) 167-168 (163-171) (<https://doi.org/10.2143/etl.82.1.2014924>)

⁸⁵ The impersonal passive —common in Latin— is not widely used in Greek and is rarely found in the NT. It is mostly used to avoid the name of God. On some occasions the future tense is used to express a command, it is called the future of order, cf. FRIEDRICH BLASS – ALBERT DEBRUNNER – FRIEDRICH REHKOPF, *Grammatica del greco del Nuovo Testamento*, Brescia, Paideia, 1982, § 130. .

⁸⁶ For example, Herod the Great, who had proceeded brutally against any possible opponent, cf. DILLMANN – MORA PAZ, *Comentario al Evangelio de Lucas*, 430.

⁸⁷ Cf. DERRETTI, “A Horrid Passage in Luke Explained (Lk 19:27)”, 136-138.

⁸⁸ Cf. BLASS – DEBRUNNER – REHKOPF, *Grammatica*, § 71, note 1.

Gospel, this violence could evoke the massacre that took place at the destruction of Jerusalem in 70 AD⁸⁹.

4.5. Narrative conclusion (19:28)

The narrative conclusion of v. 28, as indicated above, marks a new beginning as well as forming the framework of our pericope. It is presented as an application of the preceding parable: Jesus is the royal suitor who goes up to Jerusalem to receive the acclamation.

By using the term Ἱεροσόλυμα and not Ἱερουσαλήμ the author of the third Gospel emphasises the city which is opposed to the reception of the Lord. Thus, the explanation is of a theological order. Ἱερουσαλήμ (v. 28) is a sacred name: Luke uses this way of referring to the city as holy, the place of messianic appearance and of the realization of the salvific event. Ἱεροσόλυμα (v. 11) is Luke's way referring to the city on a profane level, as guilty of not having recognized Jesus as its Lord⁹⁰.

5. CONCLUDING REMARKS: PRAGMATIC FOCUSING

The pragmatic focus, as a conclusion of the present study, does not intend to limit the space of the analysis of Lk 19:11-28 in a communicative key to the final moment. In fact, some communicative elements of the text have already been pointed out, at the same time as the textual cohesion and coherence have been shown.

In this section, therefore, the communicative intention of the analysed text, which is patiently developed and constructed, will become apparent. The author, by means of strategically placed, meticulously interwoven and harmoniously

⁸⁹ Cf. DE LA POTTERIE, "La parabole du prétendant à la royauté (Lk 19:11-28)", 637.

⁹⁰ Cf. Ignace DE LA POTTERIE, "Les deux noms de Jérusalem dans l'évangile de Luc", *RSR* 69 (1981) 69-70 (57-70); Krzysztof Mielcarek, *Ierousalem Or Hierosolyma: Exploring the Semitic and Hellenistic Onomastic Notions in Luke's Work*. Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, Göttingen, 2023, 28-49, 217-238.

composed mechanisms, establishes a progressive degree of communication, which does not stop at the superficial level.

The communicative force does not end in the dialogue between author and model reader, which is always necessary and indispensable. This encounter goes a step further, continuing the dialogue between the text, the model reader and the actual readers, who, when confronted with the parable of the minas, can identify a response and guidelines for action. No one remains silent before the text: listening provokes dialogue; the encounter is projected into ever new responses⁹¹.

5.1. Trust, responsibility and mission

The analysis has shown that, from the outset, the parable proposes a twofold dimension of *trust*. In the first place, it is the king who trusts - without prior merits - his servants, hoping the possibilities of each one. Why doesn't the king distribute the money according to the servants' abilities, because he was unaware of them or because he wanted to know and value them?⁹² In one way or another, the starting point is the same for all. This reflects God's way of proceeding, who trusts man from the beginning of creation to the end of time.

The actions of the man of noble birth can only be understood on the basis of trust. He wants to establish a relationship with his servants that goes beyond what is legal and just: trust goes beyond the parameters of justice and legality⁹³. The initial trust establishes a relationship where the first word is not "I" but "here I am and here I will be"⁹⁴.

While the first dimension refers to God who trusts in man, the second reflects the action of man who trusts in God. The trust placed deserves a performance of the same type⁹⁵. The first servants believe in the ability of the mine to bear fruit

⁹¹ Cf. MORENO SANZ, *Jesús y Moisés en diálogo*, 222.

⁹² Cf. ALETTI, *El arte de contar a Jesucristo*, 123.

⁹³ Cf. Paul RICEUR, *Amor y justicia*, Madrid, Trotta, 1993, 35-55.

⁹⁴ Cf. Graciano GONZÁLEZ RODRÍGUEZ ARNÁIZ, "Confianza", in Mariano MORENO VILLA (ed.), *Diccionario de pensamiento contemporáneo*, Madrid, San Pablo, 1997, 238 (236-239).

⁹⁵ Cf. SCALABRINI, "Il primo Testamento e la ricchezza", 25.

on its own. From this perspective, the third servant breaks the relationship of trust by hiding the mine in a handkerchief: not only does he not trust himself, but he also does not trust the one who gave it to him. The communicative strategy is to reinforce a community that needs to trust God in the midst of difficulties where it is easy to be carried away by fear, doubt, uncertainty or monotony.

The relationship of trust is shown again in the accountability of the first two servants. Both respond to the king with representative acts (v. 16b; v. 18b). Neither of the two presents the minas: neither the one that had been donated, nor the fruits that it had produced. In this way, the king trusts their words as he had trusted them by giving them the mina. On the other hand, the third servant presents the mina, excluding himself from the relationship of trust.

The mina represents the trust placed in each of the servants, to take away the mine is to take away the trust from whom does not deserve it; to give the mine to the one who already has ten means to increase trust even more. The text poses the trust-distrust dilemma, which is seen in qualitative and not quantitative terms, i.e. either one has trust or one does not. In this sense, the king is prepared, from the outset, to trust everyone equally; it will be the actions of each person that will confirm or withdraw this trust.

Luke's gospel is a call to *responsibility*, either Jesus' responsibility for his own mission or the disciples' responsibility for the mission entrusted to them. The fear of the third servant makes him irresponsible. On the other hand, trust—not himself but the ability of the mine to bear fruit on its own—makes the first two servants responsible: trusting the task entrusted to them, they are trusting the One who entrusted it to them.

The question of responsibility is deeply linked to the issue of freedom⁹⁶. One can only speak of personal responsibility when there is personal freedom⁹⁷. The relationship with God is a relationship built on freedom, responsibility and constancy.

⁹⁶ Cf. DORMEYER, "La parábola de las minas", 257-258.

⁹⁷ Cf. José María AGUIRRE ORAA, "Responsabilidad", in Mariano MORENO VILLA (ed.), *Diccionario de pensamiento contemporáneo*, Madrid, San Pablo, 1997, 1045 (1044-1050).

In this way it is possible to go a long way, dominated by routine, by opposition or indifference from the outside.

In v. 17b the king entrusts the first servant with a new *mission* by a declarative act: “Have authority over ten cities”. This act is repeated in v. 19b when he entrusts a new mission to the second servant. The king, because of his new status, now has greater power which he shares with his servants. The king’s action is understood within the image that the parable projects of the Kingdom of God. The model reader is led to keep in mind the need to face ever new —often unexpected— missions, which are based on the trust of the Lord and the responsibility of the believer. The relationship is no longer that of a servant and his master, but rather that of a king and his co-workers.

On careful reflection of the parable we see that the impact on the reader is not that of two role models but of three⁹⁸. The king addresses the first servant in v. 17a with an expressive act: “good servant”. This expressive act is repeated again in v. 22a with a radically different content: “bad servant”. On the other hand, with regard to the second servant, he does not make any assessment or express his feelings. On a communicative level he expresses something else: there is an intermediate point between the actions of the first servant and the third. If the first two actions are the same, why does Luke insist on repeating them? Is it the same that he produces five minas or the profit goes up to ten? The strategy proposed by Luke is to present that the initial quantity is not important since in the end everyone will give his own answer⁹⁹. In this way, the model reader is encouraged to answer for himself, personally demonstrating how he has acted on the task entrusted to him.

The reader is presented with the ideal of the “good servant” and the “bad servant” as a warning. In this way, the action of the second servant is legitimate and reflects a community where not everyone acts and responds in the same way, but which is moving in the same direction. It is the risk

⁹⁸ Cf. ROHRBAUGH, “A Peasant Reading”, 36, preserved by Eusebius (Theophania)

⁹⁹ Cf. Guillermo STEINFELD, “¿Qué haría si no tuviera miedo...? La tensión dialéctica en el método teológico”, *Cuadernos de Teología* 25 (2006) 160-161 (141-161).

of assuming personally and communally a response to the Kingdom of God in the midst of the world¹⁰⁰.

Each of the three servants acted differently. The third servant's action is caused by his *fear* of the king. Throughout his gospel, Luke has insisted on not being afraid¹⁰¹. However, because of the disciples' own lack of understanding, fear was present in them¹⁰².

The third servant's fear is caused by a misconception of the king and becomes the cause that makes it impossible for him to act. The pragmatic strategy aims to prevent the readers from being driven by fear, especially when it is an unfounded fear. The believer who trusts in God cannot be driven by paralysing fear¹⁰³. Moreover, action, work and commitment increase courage, valour and determination, while inactivity, indifference and inconstancy increase fear and hatred, foster prejudices and justify mistrust.

The third servant is driven by uncertainty and the search for a false peace of mind that he clearly cannot find in a handkerchief. The first two servants find their security in the trust that the king has placed in them. They live from the trust that the third servant rejects and that inevitably leads him into a state of fear that paralyses him¹⁰⁴. The unknown—or more precisely, the wrongly known—provokes fear in the third

¹⁰⁰ Cf. Gerard FOUREZ, *La fe como confianza. Aliento para construir una historia nueva* (Presencia Teológica 126), Santander, Sal Terrae, 2002, 13-14.

¹⁰¹ Cf. 1:13,30; 2:10; 5:10; 8:50; 12:4,7,32. The invitation not to fear is constant in the OT, cf. Bruna COSTACURTA, *La vita minacciata: il tema della paura nella Bibbia Ebraica* (Analecta Biblica 119), Rome, Pontificio Istituto Biblico, 1988, 257-264.

¹⁰² Cf. 2:9; 8:25,35; 9:34; 20:19; 12:5; Adelbert DENAUX – Rita CORSTJENS, *The Vocabulary of Luke: An Alphabetical Presentation and A Survey of Characteristic and Noteworthy Words and Word Groups in Luke's Gospel* (Biblical Tools and Studies 10), Leuven, Peeters, 2009, 630-631

¹⁰³ "La necesidad de seguridad es fundamental ya que el ser humano no se desarrolla en la incertidumbre. La principal pulsión es la búsqueda de la seguridad [...] La seguridad no es menos necesaria para el adulto, para el cual representa una condición de la acción fecunda": Jean DELUMEAU, "Seguridad: Historia de una palabra y un concepto", en Marta Inés VILLA MARTÍNEZ (ed.), *El miedo: Reflexiones sobre su dimensión social y cultural*, Medellín, Corporación Región, 2002, 81 (71-82).

¹⁰⁴ Cf. COMPIANI, *Fuga, silenzio e paura*, 116-118.

servant, while it provokes hatred in the countrymen¹⁰⁵. Both attitudes go hand in hand in the story as they hinder the relationship of trust with the king.

In short, the pragmatic strategy aims to provoke in the reader a double action: on the one hand, to get to know Jesus as he is and, on the other hand, to open up to a relationship of trust, leaving aside the fear and hatred that paralyse any action of the believer in the midst of the community. When God, through Jesus, makes himself present in human reality, fear has no place and gives way to trust, responsibility and mission.

5.2. The time of crisis

The Lukan community is discovering time as a space to live the salvation brought by Jesus in the midst of new problems such as identity crises as disciples¹⁰⁶. Thus, v. 14 contains two expressive acts: “his countrymen hated him” (v. 14a) and “we do not want this man to reign over us” (v. 14b). Both show a hostility that reflects the situation of the Lukan community¹⁰⁷. The gratuitousness of this rejection places the reader before a paradox: the king’s greatest difficulty is not outside him, on the contrary, the opposition is born among those closest to him, his countrymen.

The danger that any ruler can fear, which is the declaration of war, is heightened in several ways. Firstly, because of the motivation: hatred. It is not that they want to achieve something specific but that the reason for sending the embassy is simply the hatred they have for him. Secondly, because it comes from within his own homeland and this makes the danger unexpected. A king usually expects danger to come from outside, from abroad, yet the countrymen—who should be the ones to defend the king in case of war—become the

¹⁰⁵ Cf. Jean DELUMEAU, “Miedos de ayer y de hoy”, in Marta Inés VILLA MARTÍNEZ (ed.), *El miedo: Reflexiones sobre su dimensión social y cultural*, Medellín, Corporación Región, 2002, 16 (9-21).

¹⁰⁶ Cf. Santiago GUJJARRO OPORTO, *Los cuatro evangelios* (BEB 124), Salamanca, Sígueme, 2024, 448-449.

¹⁰⁷ Cf. Marco LACONI, *Luca e la sua Chiesa*, Torino, Gribaudi, 1986, 17.

ones who stalk him. Thirdly, the sending of the embassy comes immediately after a praiseworthy action: while the pretender to the throne grants ten minas for ten servants —indicating a number that relates to the whole— his countrymen, either unaware of this action or knowing about it, act as they had planned beforehand.

The communicative context reflected in this way is that of a community living in the midst of a series of internal tensions resulting from its own mixed and complex composition¹⁰⁸. Although external difficulties and persecutions cannot be ignored, the parable refers to the setbacks —both timeless and universal— experienced within the community itself.

Just as the kingdom of God is “within” and does not come from “outside”, so the enemies of the kingdom are within the community itself too. Throughout the history of the Church there have always been difficulties and persecutions, but if Christianity dies, it will not die because of external enemies but because of the danger that arises from within the community itself. The greatest problem facing the Church is not persecution from outside, but rather not having a word to say, a faith to put into action and a hope to show.

The versicle 25 reflects a community of readers who do not quite understand what is happening in their life of faith. The protest of those present, rather than expressing a demand, becomes a manifestation of astonishment. They cry out against the king, so that to give a new mine to the one who has ten would be a double injustice: on the one hand, the third servant has nothing left; on the other hand, the first servant does not need it because he has too much. At the communicative level, the protest of those present reflects the reproach of all the readers, expressing their incomprehension and astonishment at what is happening¹⁰⁹. Since the text does not give an answer, it can be assumed that, as with the rhetorical question in v. 23, it is a signal from the model author for the model reader to

¹⁰⁸ Cf. Giuseppe SEGALLA, “L’etica narrativa in Luca-Atti”, *Teologia. Brescia* 20 (1995) 42-43 (34-74).

¹⁰⁹ Cf. Halvor MOXNES, *Poner a Jesús en su lugar: una visión radical del grupo familiar y el Reino de Dios* (Colección Ágora 18), Estella, Verbo Divino, 2005, 283-285.

become personally involved. The communicative context thus reflects a community that is open to the action of the Spirit, but at times does not understand God's way of acting and does not fully accept his kingdom.

5.3. From the King to the Lord

The parable of the minas does not show a single Christological dimension, but rather several images complement each other, weaving the warp and woof of a text that thus presents the richness of the face of Jesus: King, Judge and Lord¹¹⁰.

The image of Jesus as *king* is shown in an allegorical way, far from political and temporal components¹¹¹. It is a new model of a king for a new model of a kingdom. A king who trusts his servants and shares with them: first a task, then a mission. A king who is not accepted by all. The model reader is led to trust the king as the king has trusted his servants.

The image of Jesus as *judge* has a dynamic, poetic and prophetic dimension (v. 22a). The third servant with his judgement on the king makes the king become a judge for him, reflecting the image he has projected as a mirror image with him and his countrymen. In other words, the last servant and the countrymen would not have been judged if he had not ruled beforehand. The pragmatic strategy is to lead the reader to look at the kingdom of God and its king as he has intended it to be shown, leaving aside one's own expectations, interests and prejudices.

The parable underlines a third aspect that has a greater communicative force: the protagonist of the parable is the *Lord*. A careful reading of the text reveals four times the vocative *κύριε*, always referring to the king. It is used by the three servants and by those present when they express their incomprehension. In this way, Luke makes this constant appeal to

¹¹⁰ Cf. Christopher M. TUCKETT, "The Christology of Luke-Acts", in Joseph VERHEYDEN (ed.), *The Unity of Luke-Acts: Colloquium Biblicum Lovaniense* (BETHL 142), Leuven, Peeters, 1999, 139 (133-164).

¹¹¹ Cf. Antonio GARCÍA MORENO, *Jesús el Nazareno, el rey de los judíos: estudios de cristología joánica* (Colección teológica de la Universidad de Navarra 103), Pamplona, Universidad de Navarra, 2001, 143.

the Lord resonate in the ears of his readers, which goes beyond a specific action or the lack of understanding of what has happened.

At the communicative level the images of king and judge are necessary to arrive at what we consider to be the core of the Christology of this passage: the step from king-judge to Lord. Indeed it is Jesus, the King, the same one who has judged the third servant for his pre-understanding, who is presented as Lord. On a pragmatic level, the model reader is led to present before the Lord his fruits or the lack of them; his confidence or his fears. What is important is not so much what is presented, which will vary from case to case, but to whom it is presented: to the Lord.

Jesus' way of being king is a new way: a king who lives his reign in service, especially of the poorest; a king who trusts his servants. Jesus creates a new vision of reality, he restores God's original plan with his actions, he does not eliminate it, but brings it back to its original splendour. The "King" presents a model of government based on trust and responsibility. The "Lord" also shows his own life as an example and offers it unconditionally. The disciples follow Jesus as King and give their lives for Jesus as Lord. In a context where many present themselves as lords¹¹², Luke reminds his community that Jesus is the true and only Lord. Don't today's communities have the same need to contemplate Jesus as the true king, judge and Lord? In short, the journey proposed by Luke to his readers is the encounter with Christ the King-Judge in order to confess faith in Jesus the Lord.

5.4. The violent face

The third Gospel is not characterised by particularly violent elements, although some can be identified (cf. 12:5; 13:3). Precisely in the analysed parable we find two great moments

¹¹² The title Luke most frequently attributes to Jesus is that of "Lord" (*Kyrios*), precisely that which the emperors used to give themselves in order to emphasise their divine status. For Luke only Jesus is the bearer of true peace because he, not the emperors, is the Lord of all, cf. GUIJARRO OPOR-TO, *Los cuatro evangelios*, 452-453.

of violence. How can we read the texts that show a violent face of God? “Come nel Primo Testamento, anche nel Nuovo, accanto a inconfondibili enunciati e segni di amore gratuito, troviamo alcuni detti e gesti di Gesù, che tradiscono una carica di violenza e un *animus* punitivo, che lasciano piuttosto interdetti”¹¹³.

The first conflict is the confrontation of the king with the third servant. The third servant’s harsh words towards the king and the echo produced when they are repeated by the ruler do not leave the reader indifferent. The second moment of violence is found in v. 27 when the king pronounces a declarative act: “bring them and slay them before me”. However, in both cases, the narrative indicates that the king pronounces the sentence but does not carry it out, why is this so?

In the case of those who did not want him as king, the place of execution is even indicated: “in my presence” Does this leave a last chance for forgiveness? Evidently, the text does not say so, but by omitting this moment, the information the reader receives leads him to conclude that the sentence is more important than the execution of the sentence. As on other occasions, to understand what Luke is really proposing, one must move from semantics to pragmatics.

We must not forget that a word of condemnation is not the same as a condemnation¹¹⁴. Think of a mother who, in order to prevent her child from doing something wrong, goes so far as to threaten him or her. Will this mother fulfill her threat? God offers the opportunity for forgiveness, but when it is rejected, judgement appears. The parable of the minas just before Jesus’ entry into Jerusalem emphasises that in the relationship with God’s plan in Jesus there is no neutral position: either one bets on him or confronts him¹¹⁵.

¹¹³ Massimo GRILLI, “La violenza di Dio e la croce. Un contributo sull’immagine di Dio nei vangeli sinottici”, *Ricerche Storico Bibliche* 20 (2008) 141 (135-155).

¹¹⁴ “La imagen de los que acuden al juez (Lc 12,58-59) no enseña nada sobre la ejecución de una sentencia, sino que es un llamamiento muy encarecido al arrepentimiento y a la conversión” (Joachim GNILKA, *Jesús de Nazaret. Mensaje e historia*, Barcelona, Herder, 1995, 194).

¹¹⁵ Cf. БОCK, *Luke*, II, 1543.

Ultimately, death on the cross becomes the high point of violence in Luke's Gospel. Thus, on the cross, it is no longer God who judges man, but God who allows himself to be judged by humanity, responding to destructive violence with a new beginning, marked by forgiveness¹¹⁶. God never abandons man even when he sets himself against the Creator. Paradoxically, the violent face of God in the parable is a new opportunity; it is God's acceptance of man's freedom, even when it may keep him away from his own happiness. The violence is intended to provoke conversion in the believer, the repentance for his mistakes and the search for the true face of God, which is fundamentally love and tenderness.

¹¹⁶ Cf. GRILLI, "La violenza di Dio e la croce", 148.

